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**A CASE ANALYSIS OF THE BUNGKALAN PRACTICE IN AN
UPLAND COMMUNITY FROM THE PERSPECTIVE OF
AGROECOLOGY MOVEMENT**

Faculty of Management and Development Studies

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Acceptance Page

This special problem titled A Case Analysis of the Bungkalan Practice in an Upland Community from the Perspective of Agroecology Movement is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Management and Development Studies, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree Master of Environment and Natural Resources Management.

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Biographical Sketch

Lia Mai T. Alonzo is currently the Executive Director of the Center for Environmental Concerns – Philippines Inc., a non-profit and non-government organization focusing on environmental research, education, policy advocacy and campaigns. She finished her BS Community Development degree minor in Sociology from the University of the Philippines – Diliman.

ABSTRACT

ALONZO, LIA MAI TORRES. Master of Environment and Natural Resources Management. Faculty of Management and Development Studies. University of the Philippines Open University. October 2022. A Case Analysis of the Bungkalan Practice in an Upland Community from the Perspective of Agroecology Movement.

Special Problem Adviser: Dr. Ramiro Plopino,

The farmers have the highest poverty incidence among all sectors in the Philippines. They have also been greatly affected by the COVID-19 pandemic. However, the farmers of Lupang Ramos in Dasmariñas City, Cavite were able to get through the two years under the pandemic with enough food supply for their community. They point to agroecology as a social movement as the key factor. However, their community is still facing a decades-old land dispute which has threatened their access to land where they live and farm. The study therefore aims to analyze how the farmers in Lupang Ramos used agroecology to address the issues faced by their community. Particularly, it aims to describe issues on land tenure and food production, and the current agroecology practices being used by the local organization in the “bungkalan” (communal farm system) to bring about positive change while focusing on agroecology as a social movement. The study was a descriptive research, particularly a case study, which gathered data using key informant interviews and documents review. The results showed that the farmers are still facing threats of eviction with the distribution of Certificate of Land Ownership Awards still and the National Grid Corporation Project still pending. Also, there were three aspects

of agroecology as a social movement that was harnessed by the farmers through the bungkalan campaign of their organization Katipunan ng mga Lehitimong Magsasaka at Mamamayan sa Lupang Ramos (KASAMA-LR), the transformation of dominant agricultural systems through organic farming, focus on food producers' issues and rights through legal and other forms of mobilizations to assert their right to land and farm inputs, and collective action through the mobilization of their community and external organizations and institutions. With this, it can be concluded that the bungkalan campaign embodied agroecology as a social movement which resulted in the increase of food production and access to land. It is recommended that a quantitative study on the improvement of food production after the bungkalan be conducted as well as the other aspects of agroecology to deepen the understanding of this field and help improve the situation of other farmers.

Keywords: *agroecology, social movement, sustainable agriculture, collective action*

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Finally, I would like to thank my family and friends who provided encouragement throughout the course of the research.

Dedicated to:

This research is dedicated to the farmers of Lupang Ramos as a gesture of appreciation for their contribution to the knowledge on agroecology and the application thereof and in recognition of all their sacrifices for their families and their community. This is also a tribute to all food producers who sustain us through their hard work. Lastly, this is for people and organizations who are part of social movements in different advocacies who are nameless and faceless heroes and agents of change.

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Chapter One

INTRODUCTION

In the Philippines, the farmers were among the population who had the highest poverty incidence in 2018 at 31.6% according to the Philippine Statistics Authority (PSA, 2020). It has also been the poorest sector in the previous record in 2015 at 40.8%. Their situation was aggravated by the COVID-19 pandemic and they need more support in the coming years according to the Department of Agriculture (Philippine News Agency, 2021). The main challenge faced by the farmers that affected their livelihood and food production is landlessness, which is experienced by 70 percent of farmers in the country (Llanto & Ballesteros, 2003) despite the implementation of the Comprehensive Agrarian Reform Program in 1998. Also, the pressure to increase food production for the general population led to the intensive use of inorganic fertilizers and other unsustainable farming practices resulted in environmental costs (Briones, 2005).

In Lupang Ramos, Dasmariñas City, Cavite, the farmers experienced the same challenges. The land they till or cultivate was once a sugarcane plantation first established during the period of American colonization. The practice of monocrop plantation was observed to have resulted to productivity decline and poor soil quality. Because of this, the farmers lacked food as well as income. The land dispute that has been going on for generations between the original inhabitants and non-natives who purchased the lands has also affected the farmers' access to land both for their livelihood and their homes.

Through decades of struggle, the farmers and residents have formed organizations, developed their agricultural practices and other initiatives to address these problems. One of these is the “bungkalan” or communal farming system that resulted in continuous food production and access to farmlands in a time where other farmers experienced grave hunger due to the COVID-19 pandemic.

Farmers in the Philippines had many types of actions to address various challenges through the years. Agroecology is an example, which was a response to the Green Revolution program characterized by the intensive use of synthetic chemical fertilizers imposed to farmers during the term of former President Ferdinand Marcos (Institute for Agriculture and Trade Policy [IATP] & Asian Farmers’ Association for Sustainable Rural Development [AFA], 2011). In Columbia, agroecology was considered a social movement that strived for security of land tenure and sustainable agricultural practices through Peasant Reserve Zones (Acevedo-Osorio and Chohan, 2019). Similarly, in Cuba, the peasants established an agroecology movement through community organizing among the farmers (Rosset et al., 2011). In Mali, agroecology was seen more than a set of technologies by a political struggle (Sinclair, et al., 2019).

These examples showed how agroecology was perceived and applied in contexts and objectives similar to the farmers in Lupang Ramos as a social movement rather than merely a set of agricultural practices. As such, it included aims such as securing land tenure and sustainable agricultural production

through farmer-led initiatives. Therefore, agroecology as a social movement can also be used to analyze their situation in the hope that other farmers may also learn useful practices and avert challenges they faced.

A. Objectives

The study aims to analyze how the farmers in Lupang Ramos used agroecology to address the issues faced by their community.

In particular, the study aims to describe issues on land tenure and food production, and the current agroecological practices being used by the local organization in the “bungkalan” to bring about positive change while focusing on agroecology as a social movement. The intention is to present an example of how agroecology is used to present learnings that can be replicated.

B. Conceptual Framework

Figure 1. Conceptual framework of the study

Figure 1 illustrates the conceptual framework of the study. To address the issues such as the lack of access to land for food production and homes, and the lack of food, the farmers of Lupang Ramos harnessed agroecology. Particularly, three aspects of agroecology that guided this study as a social movement are transformation of dominant agricultural systems, focus on food producers' issues and rights and collective action, and the actions of farmers in Lupang Ramos reflecting these aspects such as the practice of sustainable agriculture, assertion of farmers rights and mobilization community and external support, respectively. This contributed to the achievement of the rights of farmers including the increased access to land and improved food production.

Chapter Two

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

A. History and Definition of Agroecology

The term 'agroecology' was first used by Russian agronomist named Bensin in 1928 "to describe the use of ecological methods in research on commercial crop plants". About two decades later, German ecologist and zoologist Tischler published articles on pest management and soil biology, insect biocoenosis interactions and plant protection using the same term. His approach combines ecology and agronomy and its integration of agricultural management. Italian scientist Azzi defined agricultural ecology as "the study of physical characteristics of environment, climate and soil in relation to the development of agricultural plants" (Wezel, et al., 2009).

Three other scientists, German zoologist Friederichs, French agronomist Hénin and US agronomist Klages, used the concepts of agroecology without explicitly using the term between 1930s and 1960s. In addition to analyzing ecological and technological factors, Klages also analyzed socioeconomic and historical factor influencing their production. The focus from the 1930s to the 1960s was more on the plot or field scale (Wezel, et al., 2009).

The 1970s to 2000s was known as the second major historical period of agroecology. In this period, agroecology "gradually emerged both as a movement and as a set of practices" (Wezel, et al., 2009). In response to the Green Revolution that aimed for greater intensification and specialization,

there was a continuing increase in applying ecology to agriculture. There was also research on the traditional farming systems in the tropical and subtropical developing countries. Organic farming was also discussed as an alternative model. Agroecology later was defined “as a way to protect natural resources, with guidelines to design and manage sustainable ecosystems” as mentioned by Altieri and Gliessman. Conway identified productivity, stability and equity as the main properties of agroecosystems. Later on, agroecology influenced the concept of sustainable agriculture largely at the level of farming system. In the 1990s, there was greater appreciation for agroecology as reflected in the development of USA and Europe of higher education programs on the field (Wezel, et al., 2009).

In the same period, agroecology moved “towards a larger focus on the whole food system, defined as a global network of food production, distribution and consumption” wherein the “producers and consumers are seen as actively connected parts of the system.” Francis et al. as mentioned by Wezel et al. (2009) expanded the definition stating agroecology as “the integrative study of the economic and social dimensions, or more simply the ecology of food systems.” The focus in this period was on the farm, landscape agroecosystems, and farming and food systems.

From environmentalism in the 1960s that resulted from the Green Revolution’s focus on economic returns over environmental and social impacts, agroecology was only explicitly described as a movement in the 1990s. In the

USA and Latin America, agroecology was used “to express a new way to consider agriculture and its relationships with society (Wezel, et al., 2009).

Also in the second period, agroecology came to be known as “a set of agricultural practices which aims at developing a more ‘environmental-friendly’ or ‘sustainable’ agriculture. In Mexico and Central America, agroecology was seen as “the basis for an agricultural development framework supported by ecologists, agronomists and ethnobotanists.” This included the improvement of indigenous farming practices, and “practices for the conservation of natural resources, adapted soil fertility management and conservation of agrobiodiversity.” The practice was also described by Arrignon as stated by Wezel, et al. (2009) as including “water and livestock management or anti-erosion measures as a basis for rural and sustainable development in arid and sub-humid areas.”

Through the evolution of agroecology in the experience of different countries, it was observed that the term’s definitions can be classified as a “political vision (the movement), a technological application (the practices) to achieve the goals, and a way to produce the knowledge (the science).” Wezel et al. (2009) argued however that “in spite of the existence of different approaches and definitions, the new views and dimensions brought into agroecology as a scientific discipline will help facilitate the efforts to respond to the actual challenges of agricultural production, because of the increasingly applied systems thinking and interdisciplinary research approaches.”

Wezel et al. (2009) summarized the meanings of agroecology into three types namely agroecology as a scientific discipline, movement and practice (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Diversity of current types of meanings of agroecology

Source: Wezel et al., 2009

The definition of the United Nations' FAO (FAO, n.d.) best captures the three components associated with agroecology stating that it "is an integrated approach that simultaneously applies ecological and social concepts and principles to the design and management of food and agricultural systems." Furthermore, it defines agroecology as being based on "bottom-up and territorial processes" and "on the co-creation of knowledge, combining science with traditional, practical and local knowledge of producers" thus empowering "producers and communities as key agents of change." It also "seeks to transform food and agricultural systems, addressing the root causes of problems in an integrated way and providing holistic and long-term solutions" including "an explicit focus on social and economic dimensions of food

systems.” FAO (n.d.) stated 10 elements of agroecology namely diversity, synergies, efficiency, resilience, recycling, co-creation and sharing of knowledge.

B. Agroecology as a Social Movement

According to Gliessman (2012), agroecology has the explicit goal of transforming the current globalized and industrialized food system that is not economically, socially and environmentally sustainable towards being ecologically sound, economically viable and socially just. It has its roots in resistance movements such as what was seen in the late 1960s in Mexico. The imposition of the Green Revolution transformed the thousand-year-old agricultural systems into a high input, fossil fuel-based, export-oriented and monoculture cropping system. From this emerged a movement of research and re-education on the traditional farming systems in the country that is participated by ecologists and farmers alike.

The idea that “agroecology must integrate science, technology and practice, and movements for social change”, has been enriched which made the term to mean also as a “social movement with a strong ecological grounding that fosters justice, relationship, access, resilience, resistance and sustainability,” (Gliessman 2012).

Social movements as defined by Diani (1992) are “defined networks or informal interactions between a plurality of individuals, groups and/or

organizations, engaged in political or cultural conflicts, on the basis of shared collective identities.”

According to La Via Campesina as cited by Acevedo-Osorio and Chohan (2019), agroecology as a social movement, empowers farmers to defend their fundamental rights of having access to land and a more inclusive political economy with the main objective of achieving food sovereignty. Food sovereignty, according to FAO (2014), “recognizes that control over the food system needs to remain in the hands of farmers, for whom farming is both a way of life and a means of producing food.”

In Columbia, the agroecology social movement of farmers for security of land tenure and sustainable agricultural practices pushed the government to establish Peasant Reserve Zones or Zonas de Reserva Campesina (ZRC). However, its implementation has been far from its target with the looming pressure of corporate land acquisition, Green Revolution and repression of farmers. With the previous victory resulting from the farmers’ initiatives, they continued with their movement towards the full realization of the objectives of the ZRC (Acevedo-Osorio and Chohan, 2019).

In Cuba, after the tightening of US trade embargo, the peasants launched the Campesino-a-Campesino (Farmer to Farmer) Agroecology Movement (MACAC), a social process methodology, to build a grassroots agroecology movement. This was done by the National Association of Small Farmers with the aid of La Via Campesina that aimed to achieve food sovereignty after years

of the imposition of the Green Revolution. MACAC was done by farmers who practically worked as activists convincing other farmers to transition towards agroecology. The strategy proved to be successful in increasing the rate of transition (Rosset et al., 2011).

In Mali, Africa, diverse organizations representing small-scale food producers stated in their final declaration during the International Forum on Agroecology in 2015 that agroecology was not only a narrow set of technologies but above all a political struggle requiring people to address conflicts of interests towards food sovereignty (Sinclair, et al., 2019).

In these countries, agroecology as a social movement was described as being centered on food producers particularly small farmers, the issues that they are facing and how these are best address through their initiatives.

C. Agroecology in the Philippines

Agriculture is one of the three main industries of the Philippine economy. According to the Philippine Statistics Authority (PSA), in 2020, it was reported to have a 10.2 percent share in the country's gross domestic product (GDP) (Talavera, 2021). According to the Department Agriculture (DA) Secretary William Dar, "agriculture will be a driving force as the country pushes ahead with the recovery amid the Covid-19 pandemic" (DA, 2021). However, the farmers are the poorest sector having the highest poverty incidence of 31.6 percent (PSA, 2020). This has been the trend for decades. Factors that affect

this include lopsided government priorities, lack of agrarian reform and rural infrastructures and services (IATP & AFA, 2011).

The persisting poverty among the food producers themselves has resulted in social movements through Philippine history. The movement for organic farming, which is also taken synonymously to agroecology, aims to “negate a situation in which food is available but not accessible, particularly to the poor; bring back the parts of the farming system into an ecological whole to augur closed nutrient cycle; avert the continuing loss of water, which is essential to life; help reduce greenhouse gas emission while helping to build carbon sinks; and provide for the renewal of the degrading biodiversity and productive ecosystems” (IATP & AFA, 2011).

Agroecology first “emerged as an element of resistance to the Marcos regime and the dominance of transnational corporations in local production” which was established through the Green Revolution programs. Farmers “became highly dependent on costly synthetic chemical inputs that increased their indebtedness, irreparably damaged their resource based, and endangered human and environmental health and safety” (IATP & AFA, 2011). Food producers and non-government organizations (NGOs) worked together “to develop organic standards and to advocate for the legislation necessary to promote it.” From then on, organizations such as Magsasaka at Siyentipiko para sa Pag-unlad ng Agrikultura (MASIPAG) played a crucial role in the country’s entry into the global organic movement (IATP & AFA, 2011).

Towards the 1980s, there was a call for sustainable development coming from the 1987 Bruntland report of the United Nations World Commission on Environment and Development (UNWCED). Policy proposals were also forwarded to the post-Marcos administration or the presidency of Corazon Aquino. In the mid-1990s to 2001, there was a standardization of new organic approaches and increased government involvement. In the general assembly of major organic practitioners and advocates, the standards proposed by the FOODWEB network which was established in 1996 was ratified as well as the Organic Certification Center of the Philippines that was mandated to implement these standards. And from 2001 up to 2011, there were enactments of different legislations for the promotion of organic agriculture such as the Republic Act 10068 or the Philippine Organic Law and the Executive Order No. 48 providing for the establishment of a national organic agriculture program and the formation of the National Organic Agriculture Board under the Department of Agriculture (IATP & AFA, 2011).

Organizations espousing agroecology as a science, practice and movement still persist in the Philippines and many have been formed since the 1980s. An example is MASIPAG, which has 512 member people's organizations with around 30,000 farmers reached in 63 provinces nationwide (MASIPAG, n.d). MASIPAG was included in a study that reviewed the impacts of farmer-led research supported by civil society organizations in 11 countries by the CGIAR Research Program on Aquatic Agricultural Systems and on Climate Change, Agriculture. Conducted from 2007 to 2008, the study showed that 88 percent of the organic farmers of MASIPAG reported improved food

security and 85 percent reported improved health from 2000 after applying agroecology programs and practices. This included increasing crop diversity and selecting most productive crop varieties. In addition, they reported that their crops had greater tolerance to pests and diseases. Also, the study showed that MASIPAG farmers had 17 percent higher net agricultural income than conventional farmers. From 2000 to 2007, nearly 75 percent of MASIPAG farmers reported higher incomes. Other impacts also included strengthened individual capacities, strengthened local organizational capacity, and increased involvement of women farmers. These were attributed to capacity strengthening, stimulating collective action, and advocacy work (Wettasinha, 2014).

During the pandemic, MASIPAG farmers stated that “the pandemic has also exposed the weakness of the current agriculture system” causing people to suffer from the “supermarketization of food and the liberalization of agriculture.” They are encouraging for agroecology to be the “new normal” because of its “holistic approach in ensuring just, sustainable, resilient and people-centered agricultural systems, a path towards food sovereignty and the rights of people to food.” Their partner organizations have practiced urban gardening, seed sharing and preservation, simple composting and food processing as well as local food markets to make their produce more accessible to the public. Farmers have continued with their practice of the “bayanihan” or mutual support to continue with communal work thus producing food despite the lockdowns (MASIPAG, 2020). This greatly helped not only the farmers but food supply for the general public. The undersecretary of the Department of

Agrarian Reform (DAR) Emily Padilla mentioned that farmers need assistance as the most vulnerable sector in the country and since they are “taking the cudgel for the nation’s requirements at this time of the pandemic: providing food on our table” (DAR, 2021).

Chapter Three

METHODOLOGY

The study was a descriptive research, particularly a case study, since a case study “allows in-depth, multi-faceted explorations of complex issues in their real-life settings” (Crowe et al., 2011). Case studies are also grounded in what Hodkinson et al. (2001) call a “lived reality” wherein the investigation can “strongly relate to the experiences of individuals, small groups, or organizations.”

Data were gathered using key informant interviews which allowed for in-depth analysis of the experiences of the respondents. An interview agenda was prepared to probe on the situation of the land tenure and food production in Lupang Ramos as well as the agroecological practices applied. The interviews were conducted both in-person and via online communications.

There were 12 key informant interview participants that included the officers of Katipunan ng mga Lehitimong Magsasaka at Mamamayan sa Lupang Ramos (KASAMA-LR), members of the organization from the farmers, women and youth sectors, members of MASIPAG and the legal counsel of the organization from Sentro para sa Tunay na Repormang Agraryo (SENTRA), representatives from national and regional environmental organization called the Kalikasan People’s Network for the Environment (Kalikasan PNE) national and Southern Tagalog and a scientists’ organization called AGHAM Advocates of Science and Technology for the People (AGHAM).

The six farmers from Lupang Ramos were chosen deliberately as they were the ones who were experienced while at the same time capable and knowledgeable to provide information about the bungkalan. The two representatives from MASIPAG were chosen as expert practitioners of agroecology who supported the farmers through KASAMA-LR. The legal counsel from SENTRA was chosen as the expert who handled the case on the claim to the land rights of the farmers in Lupang Ramos. The representatives from Kalikasan PNE, an organization that engages in environmental advocacy through social movements were its selected officers. An agriculturist from AGHAM had a representative who was an expert on A representative of an agriculturist from AGHAM was chosen as expert on agroecology as applied by farmers organizations. These representatives were chosen as experts in their respective fields and their knowledge of the experience of the farmers in Lupang Ramos.

Documents review was conducted to supplement the interviews as well as provide additional information. This included published journals, news articles and books.

Chapter Four

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Lupang Ramos

Lupang Ramos is a 372-hectare agricultural land, formally known as Barangay Langkaan I, in Dasmariñas City, Cavite (Figure 3). It lies beside the Governor’s Drive highway and is surrounded by a mall, subdivision, golf course and factories.

Figure 3. Map of Lupang Ramos

Source: Google Maps

According to the PSA, Barangay Langkaan 1 has a population of 26,939 in 2020 (PhilAtlas, n.d.). According to the respondents,

there are 562 houses and 2000 households. The main livelihoods are farming, driving tricycles and working in factories or the mall. The main crops cultivated in the area include string beans, eggplant, bananas, rice and corn.

B. Land Tenure, Agricultural Production and the Emergence of Social Movement of Farmers in Lupang Ramos

1. LAND TENURE

Land tenure is defined by FAO (n.d.) as the “the relationship, whether legally or customarily defined, among people, as individuals or groups, with respect to land” and land tenure systems as a way to “determine who can use what resources for how long, and under what conditions.” Furthermore, it also involves property rights such as use rights, control rights and transfer rights. Land tenure is considered as one of the most important issues in Lupang Ramos. According to an officer of KASAMA-LR, *“Paano magkakaroon ng seguridad sa pagkain na nakatuntong sa maunlad na produksyon kung walang seguridad sa lupa? Ang lupa ang buhay.”* (“How can there be food security based on improved production if our land is not secured? Land is life.”)

Lupang Ramos in the colonization era. It is important to look at the history of Lupang Ramos to identify the development of the land tenure and land tenure systems. The main periods are characterized by the ownership of friars during the Spanish colonization, the transfer of land to the American colonizers, and the acquisition of the land of EMRASON. Figure 4 provides an

Figure 4. Timeline of events in Lupang Ramos

Source: Interviews and Gantala Press Inc. & AMIHAN National Federation of Peasant Women (2019)

overview of the timeline of land ownership and main events that transpired with regards to land tenure.

Lupang Ramos was first acquired by the friars during the Spanish colonization. Around 30 families resided in the southwestern area that was called “Kamaligan”. According to the oldest residents, the farmers then worked for Tandang Kulasang Pare Dela Torre and Tandang Miyanang Ongkingco. The main crops were rice and corn. The farmers also planted banana plants and other kinds of vegetables. They paid the landowners with 50 to 60 percent of their harvest as land rent.

During the 1900s, Lupang Ramos was transferred to the American colonizers thus previously called “Lupang Kano”. Some areas were transformed into sugarcane plantations where the farmers then worked as laborers that pushed some of them to the fringes of land and forced to do “kaingin” (slash and burn method) to continue producing rice and other vegetables. This had a big impact on the farmers’ food supply.

Lupang Ramos after the colonization era. After the American colonization, the land in Lupang Ramos was sold off to different private entities. In 1965, Emerito M. Ramos Sr., through their company E. M. Ramos and Sons Inc. (EMRASON), bought the land from Manila Golf and Country Club and its name was changed to “Lupang Ramos.” However, the farmers could not remember that they were informed or consulted about the change of ownership.

Rice, corn and other vegetables were continued to be the dominant crops during that time. However, towards the 1970s, EMRASON converted many areas into sugarcane plantations through contractors who were not residents of Lupang Ramos. The farmers then either worked as laborers in these plantations or looked for other source of livelihoods.

In May 1972, EMRASON applied to the Municipal Council of Dasmariñas, Cavite for the conversion of the property into a residential subdivision later to be named “Traveler’s Live Homes” and this was approved in July 1972 through Municipal Ordinance No. 29-A. In October of the same year, former President Ferdinand Marcos signed into law Presidential Decree (PD) 27 stating that lands used for planting rice and corn should be redistributed to farmers. The law also stated that lands used for cash crops such as sugarcane were exempt from distribution. The declaration of the law as well as the presence of both cash crops, rice and corn cultivation in Lupang Ramos, caused ambiguity of the actions to take regarding land distribution among farmers.

Beginning of social movements in Lupang Ramos. In 1987, around 200 residents who were mostly farmers formed the Buklod ng Magbubukid sa Lupang Ramos, Inc. (BUKLOD). This organizing effort was prompted by the Mendiola Massacre on January 22 wherein farmers protesting the lack of government action on land reform were violently dispersed by the police and military resulting to injury to many and 13 deaths. The ideals of the protesting farmers including the right to land and decent standard of living became the compelling force and inspiration of BUKLOD members to occupy the lands that

were unused as well as those controlled by sugarcane contractors by planting crops mainly for farmers' consumption. Production of crops started from the riverside and moved towards the center of Lupang Ramos. In a way, this was a form of farmers' assertion of their right to own the land as they were the original inhabitants of the place living there for generations, taking care of the land, and having developed the land to make it productive. They were able to gather support from external organizations such as the non-government organizations (NGOs), which donated farming equipment such as a corn sheller, rice thresher, carabaos and a water pump. The farmers were able to occupy around 320 hectares of the land.

During the interviews, the BUKLOD members revealed that they experienced repression because of the agricultural activities they pursued. The landowner was said to be protected by local government unit having been provided with armed personnel or what the farmers called "*goons*". There was one instance that the goons were mobilized to stop the farmers from planting and to destroy the crops using a tractor. There was one encounter when the female farmers laid down on the street to prevent the tractors from entering while the male farmers continued to plant. In an account, Damasa Perez or Nanay Masang, a farmer, went up the tractor to stop the driver. The farmers were successful in stopping the attempted entry of the tractors. After this incident, a certain general from Camp Crame came to Lupang Ramos aboard a helicopter full of soldiers. Women farmers encircled the soldiers when they alighted that prevented further confrontation. This was sustained until the administration of former President Fidel Ramos. In 1997, armed guards built

fences in a portion of the land to control farmers' access to it. When the farmers formed a barricade to stop this, the local police dispersed them.

Lupang Ramos under the Comprehensive Agrarian Reform Program.

The signing of the Comprehensive Agrarian Reform Law (CARL) into law and the launching of the Comprehensive Agrarian Reform Program (CARP) during the administration of former President Corazon Aquino in 1988 brought hope for the farmers. They applied for land reform to gain ownership of the farmlands that they have tilled for generations hoping that the land supposed to be distributed under PD 27 will finally be awarded to them. DAR released a position that the lands of Lupang Ramos were agricultural in nature and should therefore be distributed. However, EMRASON appealed to DAR.

In 1996, the Office of the President through Deputy Executive Secretary Renato Corona dismissed EMRASON's appeal reasoning that the "property remained agricultural in classification and therefore falls within the coverage of the CARP" since EMRASON failed to comply with the mandatory requirements and conditions of Municipal Ordinance Number 1 and 29-A, Administrative Order No. 152 and since the Human Settlements Regulatory Commission and the Housing and Land Use Regulatory Board (HLURB) certified that the property was agricultural. In the same year, EMRASON filed a motion for reconsideration to the Court of Appeals (CA). The CA issued then a temporary restraining order (TRO) on the issuance of the Certificate of Land Ownership Awards (CLOAs) to the farmers and granted an issuance of a writ of preliminary injunction. DAR then filed a motion for reconsideration to the CA to lift, recall or

resolve this writ of preliminary injunction to be able to distribute the CLOAs they prepared for the farmers. BUKLOD, on behalf of the 300 farmer-beneficiaries then filed a Manifestation and Omnibus Motion to also dissolve the writ of preliminary injunction citing the violation of the CARL. In 1997, the CA ruled in favor of EMRASON declaring that the parcels of land were exempt of CARP stating that it was a residential area based on the Municipal Ordinance no. 29-A (Supreme Court, 2011). The farmers were then given a notice to vacate the area.

As a response to this unfortunate decision, the farmers set up a protest camp and a barricade Langkaan II to stop the guards of EMRASON from putting up fences around Lupang Ramos. It was again the women who were at the frontlines when they were confronted by the police in 1998 headed by a certain Major Carranza. A respondent recalled how he threw Nanay Masang aside to gain access to the protest camp.

It was after the loss of BUKLOD in their petition in the Court of Appeals that the members started to become disheartened. According to the respondents, the intervention of then Governor Bong Revilla and pressure of EMRASON convinced many farmers to stop their struggle and sell or lease the lands that they were able to collectively claim in the occupy movement. Once the lands were sold or leased, farmers would lose their control of and access to the land. From 1997 to 2000, many leaders and members of BUKLOD decided to accept defeat by acceding to EMRASON's payment. They even sold the farm

equipment that were donated to the organization as support to the occupy movement.

The farmers who wanted to continue asserting their right to the land lost trust in BUKLOD prompting them to form another organization in 2010, the KASAMA-LR. This new organization reached out for help to Sentro para sa Tunay na Repormang Agraryo (SENTRA), an organization of volunteer lawyers. SENTRA provided legal assistance and helped request the Dasmariñas City local government unit to furnish them a copy of the Municipal Ordinance No. 29-A. The office issued the statement that there was “no record on file”. When they went to HLURB, they showed that the tax declaration of the property was “agricultural in use.” The DA also stated that the property was agricultural land (Gantala Press Inc. & AMIHAN National Federation of Peasant Women, 2019). These findings were presented to DAR when Rafael Mariano was the secretary of DAR and KASAMA-LR was informed that the case was pending in the department because the farmers filed a petition for the revocation of the exemption order.

With this new update, also in 2010, SENTRA together with KASAMA-LR filed a motion for reconsideration to the Supreme Court to reverse the decision because of the absence of the Municipal Ordinance no. 29-A in the Dasmariñas City local government unit. The Supreme Court said that they should bring the matter to DAR. DAR said that the decision was final. The lawyer from SENTRA asserted that a proof of the basis of the decisions should be shown. DAR Central Office then referred the case to the provincial office for investigation.

When an ocular inspection was made, representatives from the DAR provincial office ascertained that the land was indeed a productive agricultural land. Despite this, the case is still pending.

The SENTRA legal counsel advised the farmers to stay in the lands until there was a court order served to them asking them to leave. With the farmers asserting their claim to the land, EMRASON used other tactics to force them out. EMRASON harassed the farmers together with the police. They set up an office just outside of Lupang Ramos. Some farmers reported that the police told them that they already saved bullets for them. The farmers and the legal counsel of SENTRA then filed a criminal case for these human rights violations. At this point, the legal advice was for the farmers to continue talking to DAR to reopen the case and file an intervention to DAR. Also, they said that maintaining the strong unity of the farmers was essential to prevent another incident such as the previous connivance of BUKLOD with EMRASON.

While waiting for the result of the case, the farmers continued with their cultivation of the land in Lupang Ramos. There were land still not being cultivated during that time. These lands were converted into dumpsites, neglected sugarcane plantations and lands that they believed were taken by people of EMRASON. To assert their claim to the land, in 2017, the farmers and residents of Lupang Ramos under the leadership of KASAMA-LR established the “bungkalan” or communal farm in a campaign they called “Bungkalan para sa Tunay na Reporma sa Lupa (Bungkalan for Genuine Land Reform)”. In total, they reclaimed 51 hectares of unproductive agricultural land

that used to be a sugarcane plantation but was neglected and later became a dumpsite. They made sure that there were no lands of farmers who applied to be CARP beneficiaries were covered by the bungkalan. They coordinated with DA and DAR as well as the caretaker of the land and mobilized the farmers.

Experience of civil political human rights violations of farmers. This was an unwelcome move to EMRASON and was said to have mobilized armed men to stop the efforts of the residents setting up the bungkalan. On March 3, 2018, the Provincial Government Public Safety Battalion tried to demolish the homes inside the property. However, they were not allowed inside by the farmers upon their inability to show any documents issued by the government ordering the demolition. After this incident, there were news that the government security personnel would massacre the farmers since they alleged that farmers were doing illegal actions and that they would pay 1.5 million pesos per head. This sowed fear among the farmers and consequently, because of this, almost half of the KASAMA-LR members became inactive. Three months later, on June 2, around 40 men armed with bolos and batons accompanied land agent Rudy Herrera and Langkaan Uno barangay councilor Nestor Pangilinan harassed the farmers. There was a physical confrontation and they further challenged the farmers with a gun duel (Cabico, 2018). At least two were injured (CEGP, 2018). On June 4 of the same year, armed men that farmers believed were hired by the land agent Herrera and then Barangay Councilor Pangilinan and a certain Angelito Tolentino fired at a group of farmers at around 10:00PM. Tolentino was said to be an engineer associated with-with the Ayala investors to whom the land was supposed to be sold (Fernando, 2018). The

group who were attacked was composed of around 40 individuals including farmers and students and they heard at least 10 gunshots. When the Dasmariñas City Police inspected the site, they recovered three empty shells of 9mm pistol and one empty shell of an m16 rifle (Cabico, 2018). There were also gunshots at night (Umali, 2019). Two days later, Tolentino threatened the farmers of the possibility of a bloodbath should they continue to plant crops and fight for their land. A Philippine National Police (PNP) officer was in the vicinity and heard the threat and forced the farmers to stop planting crops to avoid a fight (CEGP, 2018). In addition, a detachment was set up by the Cavite Provincial Police in front of the entrance to Lupang Ramos.

Since the farmers were unfazed by the harassment of the government and EMRASON, EMRASON again used BUKLOD to stop the farmers. Some members of BUKLOD claimed that the land was theirs and sold or leased to them. Still others became sugarcane plantations again causing the reduction of the area of bungkalan to 25 hectares.

In 2020, the residents again faced another round of forced eviction this time due to the Tuy-Dasmariñas 500kV Transmission project of the National Grid Corporation of the Philippines (NGCP) that will occupy a part of Lupang Ramos. After they received news on this threat, the farmers had a dialogue with DAR on December 21, 2020. According to residents, NGCP agents were seen trying to enter Lupang Ramos without permission since 2014. It was revealed in the dialogue that despite its claim of securing an Environmental Compliance Certificate (ECC) for the contested project, NGCP did not conduct public

consultations which was required by law thus rendering the ECC invalid. NGCP meanwhile responded expressing their plan to confer with the Regional Trial Court to have the notice of eviction delayed. Despite having a temporary victory with the NGCP transmission line, up to the present, there is still the pending case with EMRASON.

The issues of land tenure that caused farmers to assert their rights have resulted to commission of other civil political human rights violations such as the red-tagging of the leaders of KASAMA-LR, a practice wherein the government names individuals and organizations as members of terrorist or communist groups. This affected organizations that supported them including the members of the College Editors Guild of the Philippines (CEGP), an intercollegiate alliance of student publications in the Philippines, and land rights activist Emmanuel Asuncion, who was a known supporter of the farmers of KASAMA-LR, frequenting their community and joining their mobilizations. He was one of those killed on March 7, 2021 which was known as the Bloody Sunday because nine individuals were killed and six were arrested in just one day (Umali, 2021).

2. SITUATION OF AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTION

Before the formation of the organizations in Lupang Ramos in the 1950s-1960s, the families planted rice and corn. Payments for the land they used for producing rice and corn were made through sharing of what they have produced to the American landowners.

When the farms were transformed into a sugarcane plantation in the 1970s, the farmers became wage workers worked in sugarcane plantations. Farmers however recalled that the wages were not enough for their daily and regular needs. The farmers were not able to plant rice, the most important crop for them, because the land they used to till were planted with sugarcane and they were landless. In addition, it was difficult to plant vegetables even around their homes since they claimed that the soil they till were of poor quality because of decades of mono-cropping practice and intensive use of synthetic chemical farm inputs.

When the some of the farmlands were transformed into rice paddies by the members of BUKLOD in the late 1980s and became accessible to some farmers, production was low even if they applied synthetic chemical fertilizers and pesticides. This caused a rise in the expenses on farm inputs thus leaving the farmers with very little or negative income.

To offset their lack of food and income and while waiting for the harvest season, the farmers engaged in other sources of income by working as tricycle driver, and finding jobs in factories or nearby shopping mall. However, the income from these sources were also not enough. In addition, the respondents mentioned the unavailability of other sources of livelihood for them especially for those who did not finish high school or college.

With the formation of KASAMA-LR, they adopted agroecological practices which are done up to this day and were able to have plots of farmland to till.

C. Current Agro-ecological Practices

With the plan of KASAMA-LR to establish the bungkalan, they reached out to MASIPAG for help. Representatives from MASIPAG, KASAMA-LR and the farmers conducted consultations and preparatory discussion in 2017 to identify their issues, needs and requests. Among those identified were the lack of knowledge on the transformation of the monocrop plantation into rice paddies or vegetable plot, knowledge on how to transform or the lack of seeds and other farm inputs, the low supply of water for irrigation, the difficulty of convincing farmers to transition to organic farming, and the human rights violations on the farmers related to the land dispute. Despite the issues ranging from economic, social and political concerns, agroecology was deemed the best solution to address them.

MASIPAG then conducted trainings on sustainable agriculture and soil fertility management that were based on the principles of agroecology and was attended by around 60 farmers in Lupang Ramos. Some farmers were already familiar with components of agroecology such as organic farming but not comprehensively knowledgeable in other aspects such as agroecology as a scientific discipline, movement and practice. Table 1 presents the definitions of agroecology and the farmers' existing knowledge related to aspects of agroecology.

Agroecology as a social movement has three main concepts namely the transformation of dominant agricultural systems, the focus on food producers' issues and rights and collective action. It was discussed previously in this paper that the farmers wanted to practice organic farming, which they defined as farming without using synthetic fertilizers and pesticides and only using what is already available in their community. They wanted to transition to organic farming, which they believed is more sustainable since it will entail less cost in terms of inputs and produces higher yield in the long term due to soil rehabilitation. On the other hand, they were not aware that this was part of sustainable agriculture which is one aspect of agroecology (Wezel et al., 2009). They also aimed to address the root causes of their problems such as lack of access to land due to the lack of agrarian reform and the lack of support for farmers both for food production as well as other social services. They believed that these should be addressed to achieve genuine development in their community. To achieve these, they believed that the core is their united and collective action through the leadership of their organization, KASAMA-LR, while working with external institutions and organizations to have more support for their campaigns as well as to give solidarity for other farmers.

Table 1. Concepts of agroecology from different sources and from the perspective of farmers of Lupang Ramos

Concepts of Agroecology as a Social Movement	Wezel et.al (2009)	FAO (n.d.)	MASIPAG (IATP & AFA, 2011, MASIPAG, 2020 & interviews)	Farmers of Lupang Ramos (from interviews)
Transformation of dominant agricultural systems	Sustainable agriculture: aiming to achieve a higher common goal through development of traditional practices as an alternative to dominant agricultural systems	Transforming food and agricultural systems applying ecological and social concepts and principles to the design and management of food and agricultural systems	Emerged as an element of resistance to the program, the Green Revolution, of the Marcos regime where transnational corporations dominated local production due to the dependence on costly synthetic chemical inputs	Practice of organic farming as an alternative to the dominant commercial practice of extensive use of synthetic chemical fertilizers and pesticides that are more expensive and degrade soil quality and focus more on production for profit and not local needs
Focus on food producers' issues and rights	Rural development: political movement bringing food producers interests at the core	Addressing root causes of problems in an integrated way and providing holistic and long-term solutions including social and economic dimensions of food systems	There should be a holistic approach to ensure just, sustainable resilient and people-centered agricultural systems towards food sovereignty and achievement of the rights of people to food	Root causes such as the lack of access to land due to the lack of agrarian reform, and lack of support for farmers for food production and other social services should be addressed for genuine development in their community

Table 1. Concepts of agroecology from different sources and from the perspective of farmers of Lupang Ramos (continued)

Concepts of Agroecology as a Social Movement	Wezel et.al (2009)	FAO (n.d.)	MASIPAG (IATP & AFA, 2011, MASIPAG, 2020 & interviews)	Farmers of Lupang Ramos (from interviews)
Collective action	Environmentalism: action-oriented movement of farmers or social partnerships to respond to challenges where food producers are the main actors of change	A bottom-up process that empowers food producers and communities as key agents of change	The collective action of farmers through organizations and farmers' organizations nation-wide is the key to addressing the challenges of food producers	Farmers should work together through the leadership of an organization while working with external institutions and organizations for support and solidarity

Source: Wezel et.al (2009), FAO (n.d.), IATP & AFA (2011) and MASIPAG (2020)

Table 2 summarizes the practices of agroecology as a social movement done in Lupang Ramos. Details of each of the concept are described in the succeeding sections.

AGROECOLOGY COMPONENTS FOR SOCIAL MOVEMENT IN LUPANG RAMOS

This section describes the components of agroecology as a social movement namely sustainable agriculture, assertion of farmers' rights and mobilization of community and external support that were reflected in the experience of the farmers in Lupang Ramos.

Component 1: Entry of sustainable agriculture practices in Lupang Ramos. In 2017, MASIPAG conducted a training on setting up a two-hectare organic trial or demo farm (Image 1) and provided 50 varieties of native seeds of vegetables and rice. It is estimated that two years shall be needed to rehabilitate the degraded soil from monocrop plantation. Hence, farmers of Lupang Ramos planted madre de cacao/ kakawate (*Gliricidia sepium*), ipil-ipil (*Leucaena leucocephala*), malunggay (*Moringa Oleifera*) and katuray (*Sesbania grandiflora*) in the boundaries of farm plots. The leaves from these, from existing trees, food wastes and stalks of rice and corn were used as fertilizers. Nitrogen fixing vegetables were also planted to introduce nutrients to the soil while producing food that included string beans (*Dolichos sesquipedalis*), mungbeans (*Vigna radiata*), and peanuts (*Arachis hypogaea*). After one cropping, the vegetables were rotated with rice and corn. This crop rotation ensures nutrient cycling in the soil.

Table 2. Summary of the practices of agroecology as a social movement done by the farmers of Lupang Ramos

Concepts of Agroecology as a Social Movement	Actions	Actors	Achievements
Transformation of dominant agricultural systems	<p>Organic farming as a part of sustainable agriculture</p> <p>Demo farm and individual farm plots</p> <p>Setting up of bigasan (stores selling their rice produce)</p> <p>Setting up of bagsakan or farmers' markets</p>	<p>KASAMA-LR and MASIPAG</p> <p>KASAMA-LR and MASIPAG</p> <p>KASAMA-LR and MASIPAG</p> <p>SAKA</p>	<p>Mass production after one year of the establishment of bungkalan with around 20 varieties of rice and vegetables from the initial 50 varieties from MASIPAG</p> <p>Continuous food supply even during the pandemic</p> <p>Continuous source of income</p>
Focus on food producers' issues and rights	<p>Legal action and other forms of mobilizations to assert right to own the land they till in Lupang Ramos in relation to the claim of EMRASON and the NGCP</p> <p>Allotment of land for homes</p> <p>Reaching out to DA for farm inputs</p> <p>Reaching out to DENR for dialogue</p> <p>Stopping the forced entry and demolition of homes of private armed security forces and police</p>	<p>KASAMA-LR and SENTRA</p> <p>KASAMA-LR</p> <p>KASAMA-LR</p> <p>KASAMA-LR</p> <p>KASAMA-LR</p>	<p>Pending case in the SC regarding the CARP exemption not yet dismissed</p> <p>Moratorium in the NGCP project</p> <p>Setting up of homes for farmers</p> <p>Continuous food supply even during the pandemic</p> <p>Continuous source of income</p>

Table 2. Summary of the practices of agroecology as a social movement done by the farmers of Lupang Ramos (continued)

Concepts of Agroecology as a Social Movement	Actions	Actors	Achievements
Collective action	Setting up of management and farming systems (rotation, rules, dispute settlement)	KASAMA-LR	Systematic and efficient management and farming systems
	Establishing demo farm to encourage participation in bungkalan	KASAMA-LR	Increased participation of women and youth in organizational activities (educational discussions and meetings) and food production
	Conducting cultural activities to inspire youth to participate in organizational activities and food production	KASAMA-LR, MASIPAG	Improved farming practices Material and financial support from DA
	Learning exchange and collaboration with practitioners of agroecology	KASAMA-LR, MASIPAG, AGHAM	Farm inputs acquired Raising public awareness on the situation in Lupang Ramos
	Reaching out to NGOs and people's organizations, students and media	KASAMA-TK, MASIPAG, Kalikasan ST	Support for the bungkalan campaign and farmers in Lupang Ramos in general Farmers able to live and till the land in Lupang Ramos

Source: Wezel et.al (2009), FAO (n.d.), IATP & AFA (2011) and MASIPAG (2020)

Image 1. Organic trial or demo farm of KASAMA-LR

Farmers also learned how to make fertilizers by combining indigenous microorganisms (IMO) and pineapples, mangoes and rice. They also learned how to use compost and vermicompost as fertilizers instead of synthetic chemical fertilizers. Crop diversification was practiced in order to increase crop resilience to pest infestations by raising eggplant (*Solanum melongena*), bitter melon (*Momordica charantia*), squash (*Cucurbita maxima*), sweet potato (*Ipomoea Batatas*) and chili (*Capsicum frutescens*).

Agro-ecological practices such as the use of organic fertilizers, adopting crop rotation systems, crop diversification and intercropping as sustainable agriculture practices are known to improve soil health, soil biodiversity and plant protection (Leippert et al., 2020).

Since there was no existing irrigation for the crops and there was a longer dry season observed by the farmers, they raised drought resilient crops such as corn (*Zea mays*), peanuts (*Arachis hypogaea*), lady fingers/gumbo/okra (*Abelmoschus esculentus*), mung beans (*Vigna radiata*), sweet potato (*Ipomoea Batatas*) and cassava (*Manihot esculenta*). They also planted crops near a well for easier access to water. Different varieties of rice for different seasons were cultivated. During dry season, upland rice varieties that requires less water were planted. Another challenge on irrigation is the farmers' dependence on rainwater for irrigation. With the observed change in weather patterns, their planting cycle has been disrupted since it was difficult to estimate when the rains would come. With this, the farmers plotted the weather patterns to help them develop a planting calendar for identifying which crops and when to plant them.

It was articulated in interviews that some of these sustainable innovations have already been practiced by the farmers. Nonetheless, KASAMA-LR endured to share the production knowledge to other farmers for them to learn the best practices towards improve crop production in their area.

Aside from the harvest from the two-hectare demo farm, each farmer member of KASAMA-LR was also allotted one-fourth hectare of land for their own production by the organization. They were allowed to plant any crop except for sugarcane which is done by some farmers through leasing to outsiders. This was to prevent the lands from being controlled or sold by outsiders to

EMRASON that lessened their capacity to produce food for domestic consumption.

To ensure that women had the opportunity to participate and benefit from the bungkalan, KASAMA-LR ensured that they involved in cultivating the demo farm and were also given an individual farm plot if they were able to demonstrate that they had the capability and interest or commitment to manage it appropriately. The women members also managed the “bigasan” or store of the organization selling the members’ produce thus providing the farmers a steady market for their produce and also additional income for their organization. The women also managed financing for members by giving out loans to farmers in need with only two percent interest.

After just a year bungkalan was established, there was mass production in the demo farm managed by KASAMA-LR with around 20 varieties out of the initial 50 varieties that MASIPAG gave them were being cultivated. To break away from the system where the contractors benefitted from the produce by acting as middlemen, the KASAMA-LR reached out to farmers’ rights advocates including the organization Sama-samang Artista para sa Kilusang Agraryo (SAKA) to help set up “bagsakan” stalls or farmers’ markets in Metro Manila where their produce were sold. This farm-to-market system greatly helped them to increase their income for their families’ needs as well as for their farm and organization.

During the pandemic when there were long lockdowns and travel restriction that affected livelihoods and incomes, the farmers of Lupang Ramos have managed to have food to eat as well as income from selling their produce in stalls they set up along the road and in neighboring subdivisions. When the people there had difficulty in accessing food, the farmers of Lupang Ramos were able to supply them their food needs, out of the farmers' own produce from their farmlands through a community pantry (Image 2). According to the farmers, this experience made them appreciate the importance of the bungkalan and their organization and its impact on their lives. As one officer of the KASAMA-LR stated: *“Yung inaani rito ay pagkain ng komunidad. Malaki ang tulong ng tanim sa panahon ng pandemya”* (“What is harvested here is food for the community. The crops were of great help during the pandemic.”)

Image 2. Community pantry of KASAMA-LR

Cropping cycle in the community. The cropping cycle in the area as seen in Figure 5 starts in March when they start to prepare the land. This is the time that they apply organic fertilizer or plant nitrogen fixing legumes such as

peanuts. They start to plant rice on May in time for the wet season in June and July that will bring rains to irrigate their crops. They harvest the rice crops in August and let the husked rice dry before being brought to the thresher. A few farmers plant upland rice varieties that do not need much irrigation in September and harvest in December. Most of the rice harvested are used for everyday consumption of the farmers' families while some are set aside for the bigasan.

Aside from rice (*Oryza sativa*), they also plant vegetables such as eggplant (*Solanum melongena*), string beans (*Dolichos sesquipedalis*) and bitter melon (*Momordica charantia*). One farmer said that he earns 3,000 to 4,000 pesos a week during the harvest of string beans alone. After the first harvest of rice in August, some farmers plant corn which can be harvested after 65 days. They plant mung beans starting September after the first harvest of rice and harvest around March. They are then able to sell this for 80 pesos per kilo.

All through the year, many farmers plant different varieties of bananas such as lakatan (*Musa acuminata* AA Group 'lakatan'), latundan (*Musa acuminata* × *M. balbisiana* AAB Group 'silk') and seniorita (*Musa acuminata* AA Group 'seniorita') as well as root crops such as sweet potato (*Ipomoea Batatas*) and cassava (*Manihot esculenta*). Planting fruits and root crops are done to ensure a continuous supply of food and income especially if there is occurrence of environmental disasters such as droughts or typhoons that affect their main crops.

Figure 5. Cropping cycle of KASAMA-LR farmers in Lupang Ramos

Component 2: Focus on food producers' issues and rights. KASAMA-LR organized the farmers towards achievement of the common goal of asserting their rights. The rights that they have been and still are asserting through different initiatives as well as the legal basis are: the right to own the land they till as stated in the CARL of 1988 (RA No. 6657); right to farm inputs and services and right to organize according to the Magna Carta of Small Farmers (RA No. 7607); right to freedom of expression and right to freedom of information according to the Bill of Rights of the 1987 Constitution of the Republic of the Philippines; right to life, liberty and security of person, right to an adequate standard of living according to the United Nations' Universal Declaration of Human Rights; right to participate in activities against violations of human rights and fundamental freedoms, right to food and right to freedom from hunger according to the United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Peasants and Other People Working in Rural Areas.

Some of the original residents of Lupang Ramos remembered that their grandparents have been asserting their right to the land. As a matter fact, the struggle for their rights was passed on from generation to generation. They shared too that the reason why they were still living in Lupang Ramos and sustaining their crop production in the area is because of the establishment of their organization, the BUKLOD. It created a turning point in the community by bringing together the farmers and systematizing their efforts. However, it was also the members of the organization, particularly those who were demoralized and sold their lands to EMRASON, who triggered off the disunity among the community members, thus obstructing their struggle.

Up to now, they are still earning the trust of the farmers who believe in the power of united action under the collective leadership of an organization.

However, despite the setbacks experienced by the KASAMA-LR, the farmers' greatest victory was being able to live in Lupang Ramos and cultivate their farmlands. This was achieved through the filing of the appeal on the CARP exemption through the support of allied organizations particularly SENTRA and the exposition of the invalid ECC of the NGCP project in 2020 as mentioned in the previous section. They were able to achieve this not only through dialogues with government agencies and filing legal cases but also through other forms of mobilizations. These included the farmers' setting up of the protest camp in Lupang Ramos (Philstar.com, 2018), joining the protest caravan of Kilusang Magbubukid ng Pilipinas (KMP) with farmers from other provinces from Central Luzon in June 2018 (Cervantes, 2018) and January 2021 (KMP, 2021) and conducting rallies in government agencies from 2018-2021. They were undertaken to pressure related government agencies such as DAR and the local government of Dasmariñas City to take action and to call their attention to the issues at hand.

Aside from the demo farm and individual farm plots and homes within Lupang Ramos, the farmers were also able to acquire farm inputs from the government including seeds and vermin compost, a tractor (Image 3) and production subsidy from the DA. They shared that without the pressure of the

organization, they would not have received these services since they were perceived as illegal occupants by EMRASON.

Image 3. Tractor of KASAMA-LR

The farmers were also able to assert their right to land, adequate standard of living, homes, exercise their freedom of expression and security of person by confronting the private security armed groups of EMRASON, the local government unit as well as the police. Despite many attempts, these entities were not able to dismantle the protest camp, stop their rallies, demolish homes and destroy the crops of the farmers. Despite the continuous harassment and intimidation, the farmers have informed themselves of steps to take such as proper documentation so that they can file legal cases later on.

The experience of KASAMA-LR and the farmers of Lupang Ramos showed that they were able to assert their rights through various mobilizations that can be summed up as legal actions (i.e. filing of cases in court), lobbying with government agencies (i.e. dialogues with DAR and Dasmariñas City local government) and pressure actions (i.e. rallies and protest camps).

Component 3: Strengthening collective action within the community and with external organizations and institutions. According to de Molina et al. (2020), “the agroecological movement is a social movement that self-organizes around a rationale of collective action” and this paper uses their definition of collection action which are “forms of individual action coordinated in a voluntary and cooperative way whose purpose is shared by all those taking part in the action.” This section describes the collection done by farmers of Lupang Ramos.

The collective action in Lupang Ramos can also be considered as multilevel. Multilevel collective action is defined by De Molina et al. (2020) as “collective action that synchronically intervenes, modifies, at two levels, at least, of the social complexity scale, for example in farms and in the locality or nearby peasant community.” They state that the “agroecological movement has the power to generate a synergy effect and positive feedback between these three circuits of action to generate scale changes in the agroecological transition”

with the three circuits pertaining to “the most basic scale of the farm, to the immediate community scales or the political scales of the State.”

To improve food production, at the organizational level, KASAMA-LR established a rotation system for working in the bungkalan including both the demo farm and their individual farmlands (Image 4). They practiced “bayanihan”, or the practice of helping others without monetary compensation, from the clearing of the farms up to crop harvesting (Image 5).

Image 4. Individual farmland of a KASAMA-LR member

Image 5. Bayanihan of KASAMA-LR members

However, there was a decline in the number of farmers who became active in the demo farm. The organization started with 250 families working together but now only 120 families are active, comprising of about 165 farmers or individuals. The numbers declined since farmers who did not comply with the policies of the organization were removed from the rotation system. Farmers' infraction included not showing up to their schedule in the rotation system and leasing out their farmlands. There were also those that either lost interest in farming or focused on engaging in other livelihoods.

To help the farmers sell the produce from the demo farm and individual farmlands, KASAMA-LR members helped each other either to look for buyers or sell their crops in nearby subdivisions.

Special attention was given by KASAMA-LR to the youth in Lupang Ramos since they were observed to lose interest in working on the land and since the farmers were mostly in their 50s and would soon not be physically able to work in the farms. With this, the youth was also organized to become part of the rotation team for the demo farm and the bayanihan for the individual farm plots. They were also engaged in cultural activities to encourage other youth to join the agricultural activities. They created a song about the importance of unity in Lupang Ramos and this was used to raise awareness on their experience when engaging with people outside of their community.

To ensure the harmony and efficiency of production, KASAMA-LR developed a set of rules for farmers who showed interest to join the bungkalan. This included the imperatives of not selling or leasing out their lands and following the schedule of the work rotation. A system of settling disputes among their members to avoid further and more serious conflicts has also been developed and enforced. For instance, instead of bringing the members who are in conflict with the barangay, they called them to a meeting where officers of KASAMA-LR presided the discussion of issues.

At the community level, residents who are both members and non-members of KASAMA-LR were encouraged to pursue collective action thru the demo

farm since it has shown the benefits of having an organization and of collective action. They hoped that this would make other community members voluntarily join KASAMA-LR.

The initiatives on food production mentioned above were supported not only by their community but also by other local, regional and national organizations. Through the networking efforts of KASAMA-LR, they were able to gain the support of MASIPAG that imparted technical and organizational knowledge on agroecology as well as farm inputs. SENTRA has additionally provided legal assistance as a result of the networking effort. Aside from these, they also joined Katipunan ng mga Samahang Magbubukid sa Timog Katagalugan (KASAMA-TK), a regional organization of agricultural workers, which helped them reach out to other organizations. From there, direct communications and coordination with these organizations were established for future collaborative actions.

One of the abovementioned organizations of scientists called Advocates of Science and Technology for the People (AGHAM) pledged that they would encourage their members to have a learning exchange with the farmers. This resulted to organizing a series of integrations and learning exchanges of scientists in the community. AGHAM also produced information materials about the situation of Lupang Ramos which were released on their social media accounts.

KASAMA-LR also reached out to the national environmental campaign network Kalikasan People's Network for the Environment (Kalikasan PNE) through its local chapter, Kalikasan – Southern Tagalog (Kalikasan-ST), for support in their campaign. The network supported the farmers by monitoring of violations of human rights on members and supporters of KASAMA-LR. This was part of their campaign to defend environmental defenders in the country. They conducted a fact-finding mission in the region which included the case of Manuel Asuncion from the Bloody Sunday incident.

Students from universities in the region such as De La Salle University – Dasmariñas and the University of the Philippines Los Baños have also visited Lupang Ramos and conducted integration and solidarity activities. This has helped increase the awareness of the youth on the issue of the farmers through various informational materials which were released in online platforms.

The organization has also reached out to mainstream and alternative media to report on their situation. There were articles and a book written, and videos produced and released about Lupang Ramos.

These initiatives created a movement of different sectors and in different areas in support of the bungkalan. Their support created visibility and pressure for the local government and its agencies to take action. KASAMA-LR believed that without these, they would not have gotten material and financial support from the DA as well as ensured of being able to live and till the land in Lupang Ramos.

KASAMA-LR frequently hosted integrations and solidarity activities showing their visitors what they have achieved throughout the years. Aside from gaining support for their campaign, they also viewed these initiatives as a way of sharing their learnings to help other organizations in their own advocacies, whether they are pro-farmers or not. This for them was a form of bayanihan to fellow rights advocates and Filipinos in general.

Chapter Five

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

The three components of agroecology as a social movement namely transformation of dominant agricultural systems, focus on food producers' issues and rights and collective action as practiced by the farmers in Lupang Ramos are interrelated and inseparable. Transforming dominant agricultural systems is part of addressing the farmers issues and upholding their rights. Also, collective action is needed to work towards these goals. Moreover, upholding certain rights such as right to freedom of expression, right to information and right to security of person ensure collective action. All of these contributed to addressing the main issues of the farmers of Lupang Ramos particularly the lack of access to land and declining food production.

These components also change our paradigm of food producers, particularly of farmers, as the central factor in food production. This means that addressing food security means addressing their needs, and providing support for agricultural development and for farmers to become the main actors of change. This highlights as well the importance of role of government policies and agencies who are mandated to provide this support.

In addition, the experience of Lupang Ramos of adopting agroecology as embodied by the bungkalan campaigns showed the need for an organization to unite, lead and consolidate the community towards their objectives. The formation of KASAMA-LR was cited the key factor in their successes.

On the other hand, they cited disunity and individualism as the main challenge throughout their decades of community mobilization. The cooption of community leaders and members of BUKLOD to give up in their struggle led to the breaking apart of the organization and disunity of residents. One contributor to this is their perceived lack of accomplishments throughout the years. Changing dominant systems is in fact not a short journey but one which is riddled with hardships and sacrifices. State violence and lack of enabling environment for democratic participation remains a challenge. This is shown with the incidents of physical violence, harassment, arrests and killings of the farmers who stood up for their rights.

Despite these challenges, KASAMA-LR and the residents of Lupang Ramos proved to be a testament of the potential of agroecology as a social movement. Even if they are still facing threats to eviction among other issues, the lessons from their experience and initial achievements have provided the foundation for their success.

Chapter Six

RECOMMENDATIONS

From the findings of the study, it is recommended that more research be done on the improvement of food production in Lupang Ramos after the bungkalan by looking into quantitative data on the increase in food produced as well as income. In addition, studying how the different aspects of agroecology, particularly as a science and practice, would give more understanding and knowledge on experience of Lupang Ramos in the hope of drawing lessons that can be replicated and developed to improve the lives of the farmers in the country.

Based on the success of KASAMA-LR, it is recommended that local farmers' organizations be established in agricultural communities and an emphasis be placed on organizations development. This might be best led by the farmers themselves and can be supported by NGOs, civil society organizations as well agroecology and farmers' rights advocates.

For government agencies that are mandated to support and uphold farmers' rights and welfare, it is recommended that there be more transparency and access to information on projects, activities and policies that involve farmers and farming communities so that they can make informed decisions regarding these. Also, it is recommended that consistent and genuine consultation be pursued to ensure that farmers' opinions are heard and considered, and their needs are met. Furthermore, farmers should be given a significant role in decision-making when it comes to interventions that affect their land, livelihood and general wellbeing. This will help ensure a participatory

approach in providing services and implementing development programs so as to avoid misunderstanding and conflicts.

For farmers' rights and agroecology advocates, it is recommended that they engage in community integrations and investigations to better understand the issues of farmers. This can help advocates to have a comprehensive view on the situation that can guide them in supporting the farmers.

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